

Under these conditions Co^{II} reduction peak appeared with $E_p = -1.18$ V. The minimum detection limit observed for Co^{II} was 0.4 ppm with a relative mean deviation of $\pm 2.8\%$. $\text{As}^{\text{III}} \rightarrow \text{As}^{\text{0}}$ reduction peak was obtained at $E_p = -0.380$ V. The minimum detection limit of As^{III} was 0.1 ppm and relative mean deviation was $\pm 1.02\%$.

Two calibration curves each for Co^{II} and As^{III} were obtained. In case of As^{III} , range was from 0.1 to 1.0 ppm and 1 to 10 ppm; with cobalt those extended between 0.4 to 2.6 ppm and 3 to 20 ppm. They are linear over the entire range of concentrations.

Tolerance of other cations in the determination procedure was also studied. Of the two, arsenic determination procedure shows higher tolerance towards most of the ions studied as when compared to cobalt determination procedure. Pb^{II} interferes seriously with As^{II} , while Zn^{II} and Ni^{III} interfere similarly in Co^{II} determination. The presence of 50 fold excess of Hg^{II} , Co^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} are tolerated in As determination. Presence of 8 fold excess of Pb^{II} and Hg^{II} are tolerated in Co determination.

An added procedural advantage is the possibility of simultaneous determination under the set experimental conditions. Both Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} can be determined in presence of As^{III} as they have widely differing E_p values (-0.24 and -0.9 V for Cu and Ni, respectively) and give appreciable diffusion current. 2 to 30 ppm of Cu^{II} could be determined with an error of $\pm 1.8\%$, while Ni^{II} could be determined in the concentration range of 6 to 30 ppm with an error of $\pm 1.6\%$.

So as to enhance the applicability of the method developed for arsenic determination to various samples, its selective separation from other contaminants of sample matrix was undertaken. As^{III} was distilled as its trihalide (AsCl_3). Further, after the sample digestion step As will be in As^{V} form and needs to be reduced to As^{III} state for the purpose of determination. This is achieved by the use of hydrazine sulphate as reductant^{1,2,10}. To a standard solution containing 50 μg of As^{III} , 25 ml of 6N HCl, 5 ml HBr solution and 0.5 g hydrazine sulphate was added; this mixture was then distilled at a temperature of 98° for 30 min. The distillate was collected in ice-cold water and arsenic content was determined by the above developed procedure after suitable dilutions. A 96% recovery of As^{III} with a relative mean deviation of $\pm 2.1\%$ was observed.

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Titrimetric Determinations Using Bromohydantoin as a New Oxidimetric Titrant in Aqueous Medium

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AS part of our programme for the investigation of new redox titrants¹⁻⁷, we report on the use of the sodium salt of 1-bromo-5,5-dimethylhydantoin as a new oxidimetric titrant in aqueous medium. For convenience, it may be called 'Bromohydantoin'(BH). Two types of direct titrations, potentiometric and visual indicator, have been developed for the determination of some common but diverse type reductants using this oxidant. The results of these determinations are presented in this note.

Experimental

BH was prepared from dibromohydantoin, which in turn, was prepared by the bromination of 5,5-dimethylhydantoin as reported earlier^{8,9}. Dibromohydantoin (28.6 g) was added in small quantities with stirring to a solution of sodium hydroxide (6 g in 50 ml water). On cooling to 5°, crystals of BH were separated and were filtered and dried

over phosphorous(V) oxide. The purity of the sample was determined by elemental analyses. Approximately decinormal ($\sim 0.05 M$) solution of BH was prepared (14.6 g dry sample in 1 dm³ of water). This solution was fairly stable when kept in amber coloured bottle. For accurate work, daily standardisation of the oxidant is recommended. The usual iodometric method was employed for the standardisation of BH solution.

The following 10 reductants were chosen for the present investigation: antimony(III), arsenic(III), iron(II), ferrocyanide, ascorbic acid, hydroquinone, semicarbazide, hydrazine, phenylhydrazine and isonicotinic acid hydrazide. Standard solutions ($\sim 0.1 N$) of these reductants were prepared by the reported methods⁸ and their strengths were checked by standard methods^{9,10}.

For potentiometric titrations the same apparatus and electrode assemblies described earlier⁶ were used. For direct visual titrations quinoline yellow indicator was employed. The usual procedures were followed for both potentiometric and visual titrations using BH as the titrant. All titrations were carried out in *ca.* 2 *N* hydrochloric acid medium at room temperature ($30 \pm 2^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

Results of the titrations are presented in Table 1. During the titration, BH is reduced to 5,5-dimethylhydantoin as per the half-cell reaction,

where $\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2$ part. The reduction product of BH has been identified to be the hydantoin by spectral analysis of the isolated products in selected cases.

TABLE 1—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATIONS USING BROMOHYDANTOIN

Reductant	Titrimetric method	Range of reductants taken m mol	Standard deviation* μ mol	Maximum error %
Antimony(III)	a	0.21-0.43	1.3	0.47
	b	0.63-1.27	3.0	0.48
Arsenic(III)	a	0.25-0.51	0.9	0.47
	b	0.50-1.02	2.3	0.46
Iron(II)	a	0.44-0.90	1.6	0.45
Ferrocyanide	a	0.39-0.79	0.8	0.33
	b	0.21-0.43	0.5	0.38
Ascorbic acid	a	0.51-1.03	3.4	0.49
	b	0.22-0.45	0.8	0.45
Hydroquinone	a	0.12-0.25	0.4	0.41
	b	0.30-0.61	2.7	0.46
Semicarbazide	a	0.11-0.24	0.3	0.41
	b	0.27-0.58	2.2	0.49
Hydrazine	a	0.12-0.26	0.4	0.47
	b	0.32-0.65	3.9	0.33
Isonicotinic acid hydrazide	a	0.12-0.26	0.4	0.40
	b	0.31-0.64	3.5	0.41

a = Direct potentiometric method,

b = Direct visual indicator method,

* Six replicates.

All the 10 reductants can be conveniently determined by direct potentiometric method in acid medium using BH as the titrant. For each titration 10 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid is added and the reaction mixture diluted to 50 ml in order to maintain the overall acidity of the system at 2 *N*. There is no need to add any other reagents, such as bromide for the success of the titrations. The potential breaks obtained at the equivalence points for the addition of 0.1 ml of 0.1 *N* oxidant are in the range 100-300 mV as detailed below. Thus, 100 mV is recorded for antimony(III), arsenic(III), ferrocyanide and hydroquinone; 200 mV for iron(II), semicarbazide, phenylhydrazine and isonicotinic acid hydrazide; and 300 mV for ascorbic acid and hydrazine. In the case of iron(II) there is no need to add phosphoric acid unlike in the cases of other reagents developed earlier¹⁻⁶.

Direct visual titrations using quinoline yellow indicator are possible only for 7 reductants. The 3 reductants, *viz.* iron(II), ferrocyanide and hydroquinone for which visual titrations are unsuccessful using BH, give yellow coloured products on oxidation. Therefore, colour change of the indicator (yellow to colourless) can not be seen in these three cases. In all the other 7 cases, simple titrations without adding any other reagents are possible in hydrochloric acid medium. It is interesting to note that there is no need to add potassium bromide for these titrations in spite of the fact that addition of bromide is essential for the titrations using quinoline yellow as indicator. Here one of the reduction products of BH is bromide, which will react with BH again to get bromine required for the bromination of quinoline yellow to give a sharp end-point. This is a clear advantage of BH over other reagents developed earlier.

The results show that all the reductants undergo their usual oxidation schemes^{6,7}. Thus, antimony(III) is oxidised to antimony(V), arsenic(III) to arsenic(V), iron(II) to iron(III), ferrocyanide to ferricyanide, ascorbic acid to dehydroascorbic acid, hydroquinone to quinone and the hydrazine parts in the other 4 reductants are oxidised to molecular nitrogen. Both potentiometric and visual titration procedures using BH as the titrant are very accurate and precise. The titrations are reasonably fast and the equivalence points (potentiometric titrations) and the end-points (visual titrations) are very sharp. Potentiometric procedure renders the direct determinations of the reductants in the semimicro levels, while the visual titration procedure is used for macro level determinations. Thus, bromohydantoin (BH) can be used as a suitable oxidimetric titrant for the determinations in the semimicro as well as in the macro levels.

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Search for Yeast Strains Suitable for Large-Scale Production of Fat : Effect of Nitrogen Deficiency on Accumulation and Composition of Fat in Some Yeasts

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THE search for a microbial source of fat, alternative to the conventional ones, viz. plant and animal, was initiated during the World War-II¹. In the face of the recent world wide shortage of fat this search has been revitalised and it has been found that yeasts are the most suitable organism for this purpose². While choosing a yeast strain suitable for large-scale production of fat, the most important property that has to be considered is its oleaginicity, i.e. its capacity to accumulate fat in the cells. Fat accumulation in oleaginous yeasts is known to be enhanced when grown in media of low nitrogen and high sugar content¹. As the possible uses of a fat is determined largely by its composition, this factor is also very important in the large-scale production of fat from yeasts. We report here the results of nitrogen starvation on accumulation and composition of fat in cells of two strains of yeast which have been isolated by us from local soil. Of these two, the red one was characterised and designated as *Rhodotorula glutinis* Y₃³, the other strain (white) was found to be a *Candida* species but was not further characterised⁴. The results were compared with those of seven other yeast strains obtained from the National Chemical Laboratories, Poona. The two media used for growth of the yeasts were,

(i) *Complex medium*: glucose, 20 g; peptone, 5 g; malt extract, 3 g dissolved in 1 l distilled water; pH adjusted between 6.4 and 6.6, and (ii) *Nitrogen negative medium*: glucose, 20 g; KH₂PO₄, 0.8 g; K₂HPO₄, 0.2 g; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.2 g; NaCl, 0.2 g; CaCl₂·2H₂O, 0.05 g; Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O, 0.5 mg; Na₂WO₄·2H₂O, 0.5 mg; FeSO₄·7H₂O, 0.025 g dissolved in 1 l distilled water, pH adjusted between 6.4 and 6.6.

The yeast strains were grown in conical flasks (1 l) containing 250 ml of the complex medium on a gyratory shaker at 25° upto early stationary phase of growth. The cells were harvested by centrifugation at 4°, made free of nitrogenous materials by repeated washing with cold sterile water and centrifugation. A part of the washed cells were lyophilised and stored in deep-freeze for lipid extraction. A suitable portion of the rest of the washed cells was inoculated into the nitrogen-negative medium so that the cell density corresponded to an O.D. (590 nm) between 2 and 2.5. The cells were allowed to grow at 25° upto 96 h. The nitrogen starved cells were harvested, washed and lyophilised for fat extraction.

From a known amount of lyophilised cells, fat was extracted according to the method of Bagchi and Dutta⁵. Total phosphorous (mol %) in the fat was estimated according to the method of Ames⁶; this data was converted to weight percentage of total phospholipids (as distearoyl lecithin) on multiplication with a factor of 25.4. The non-polar components, i.e. triglycerides (TG), sterol-esters (SE), free fatty acids (FFA) and sterols were separated by tlc on silica gel G plates (preparative) developed in hexane-diethyl ether-acetic acid (80:20:1.5). The fluorescent bands due to these components, located by observing the chromatogram under uv-light after spraying lightly with a 0.2% methanolic solution of 2',7'-dichlorofluorescein, were scraped into small columns, their contents extracted with diethyl ether and isolated by removal of the solvent⁶. Sterols and SE were determined colorimetrically⁷. Mixed methylesters were prepared from TG and FFA by methanolysis in the presence of alkali⁸ and BF₃⁹, respectively. Percentages of TG and FFA were determined by glc of the corresponding mixed methyl esters with methylpentadecanoate added as internal standard¹⁰.

Under nitrogen starvation, the cells of most of the strains were found to accumulate higher amount of fat than under nitrogen sufficient condition (Table 1). This increase was most prominent in *R. glutinis* Y₃ (from 18.0 to 55.1%) followed by *L. starkeyi* (from 23.0 to 37.1%), the increases being 3.1 and 1.6 fold, respectively. A 3.5 fold increase in the fat accumulation was also observed with *H. anomala* cells but the final fat content was quite low (4.1%). In the cases of *S. cerevisiae* and the untyped *Candida* species cellular fat depleted due to nitrogen starvation. Thus *R. glutinis* Y₃ proves to be a yeast strain that can accumulate substantial amount of fat in the cells which increases to a very

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